

Stakeholders' Involvement in Improving Student Behavior and School Discipline in Primary Schools in Cambodia

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ABSTRACT

This study details the outcomes of efforts made by stakeholders to *adopt school management, teachers, community and ministry parent's* involvement programs in order to improve student behavior and school discipline. This study has been conducted at primary schools, in Kandal province in Cambodia. Data were collected through interview to explore participants' perception on student behavior and school discipline. Using data from primary schools, analyses show the percentage of students who misbehavior, of the prior rates of discipline in the schools, the more school management and community involvement programs were implemented, the less students were disciplined by being sent to the principals' offices, given detention, or suspended from class. The two types of involvement that are most correlated with a decrease in the percentage of pupils who require school discipline are parenting and volunteering. Additionally, schools with better stakeholders' programs reported having fewer pupils who needed to be disciplined. Qualitative methods are used for data analysis. The findings imply that there are few stakeholders work as volunteering to improve student behavior and school discipline.

KEYWORDS: Stakeholders, Student Behavior, School Discipline, Parental Involvement, Educators, Administrators, Community Engagement, Positive Behavioral Interventions, Collaboration, Academic Success, Mentorship Programs, Policy Development, Classroom Management, Educational Environment, Conflict Resolution

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction to research

Education plays a crucial role in shaping both individuals and societies, serving as a vital instrument for personal growth and social advancement. It is not only essential in Cambodia but across the globe, where the significant of education is fostering positive **student behavior** and **school discipline**. By equipping students with knowledge, skills, and ethical values, education empowers them to become responsible citizens and active participants in their communities (Dalenogare, Benitez, Ayala, & Frank, 2018).

Schools have implemented various strategies to improve student behavior and school discipline in primary schools, including: **teachers training, good connection with parents, Counseling and Support**

Services, disciplinary action (Osher, Bear, Sprague, & Doyle, 2010).

Ministry of Education has implemented several initiatives to improve student behavior and school discipline in primary schools, including: **Training for Educators, Engaging Parents and Communities**

In recent years, in Cambodia, Ministry of Education has been a lot of discussion about how student behavior and school discipline are related. Schools must balance maintaining a secure and effective learning environment with addressing the underlying causes of disruptive conduct as behavioral difficulties among students become more common. This essay will investigate how schools can effectively control students' conduct through discipline and other

interventions, as well as the different social, psychological, and environmental aspects that affect student behavior. A happy and healthy learning environment may be promoted for all children by educators through better understanding the intricate dynamics of student behavior and school discipline.

1.2. Problem Statement

Now, the student behavior at primary schools still not good enough, and also school discipline in Cambodia (Benveniste, Marshall, & Araujo, 2008). The lack of collaboration among these stakeholders is the challenge in improving students behavior and school discipline (Njoroge, Nyabuto, & research, 2014). This study seeks to provide insights into **effective methods** in improving student behavior and school discipline in primary schools (Ajowi, Simatwa, & Reviews, 2010). This research aims to provide **quality of education** in improving student behavior and school discipline in primary schools (Ron Nelson, Martella, Marchand-Martella, & Disorders, 2002).

The problem of improving student behavior and school discipline is a complex issue that affects many schools in Kandal, Cambodia. In many schools, students exhibit a wide range of behavior problems that can disrupt the learning environment and negatively impact academic achievement. These behaviors may include disruptions in class, bullying, disrespect towards teachers, and other forms of misconduct (Al-Amarat, 2011). Schools face the challenge of finding effective ways to improve student behavior and discipline without resorting to punitive measures that may exacerbate the problem. The goal is to create a positive school culture where students feel safe, supported, and empowered to learn and grow.

1.3. Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to provide insights into effective strategies for improving student behavior and promoting positive school discipline. By identifying which interventions are most effective, this study will contribute to the development of evidence-based approaches to addressing this critical issue. The results of this study will be useful for educators, policymakers, and researchers who are interested in improving student behavior and promoting a positive school culture. By the end of the introduction, the reader should have a clear understanding of the research objective and the significance of the study.

The study's particular research objectives were as follows:

1. To examine how stakeholders are involved in improving student behavior and school discipline

in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province.

2. To find out how school principals collaborate with stakeholders in improving student behavior and school discipline in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province.
3. To ascertain the challenges encountered in improving student behavior and school discipline in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province.
4. To explore what has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behavior and school discipline in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province.

1.4. Research questions

The main objective of this study is to identify effective strategies for improving student behavior and promoting positive school discipline. By answering this research question, this study will provide important insights into evidence-based approaches to addressing this critical issue. The results of this study will be useful for educators, policymakers, and researchers who are interested in improving student behavior and promoting a positive school culture. By the end of the introduction, the reader should have a clear understanding of the research question and the significance of the study.

The study's particular research questions were as follows:

1. How are Stakeholders involved in improving student behavior and school discipline in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province?
2. How do school principals collaborate with stakeholders to improve the student behaviors and school disciplines in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province?
3. What are the challenges in improving student behavior and school disciplines in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province?
4. What has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behaviors and school principals in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province?

1.5. Research Significant

This study can contribute to the school principals, teachers, parents or community, students such as:

Offers several key contributions to school principals: The study provides how principals can effectively engage various stakeholders including teachers, parents, students, and community members in addressing student behaviour and disciplinary

practices, learn how to find conflict resolution, relationship-building.

Contributions to teachers: This study provides how teachers create social media to collaborate with students' parents to ask or share student study, teacher can know how to solve the challenges or how to overcome the challenges, provide the effective disciplinary action and school regulation.

Parents/community: 1) To inform to be actively engage improving their children behavior having self-discipline, 2) encourage student to obey parent, teachers and others 3) parenting or helping all

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Direct stakeholders and Indirect Stakeholders Involvement

2.2. Direct Stakeholder:

Role of the Director: The director plays a pivotal role in shaping the school's environment and culture. Their responsibilities include (Daly-Smith et al., 2020).

Vision and Policy Development: The director establishes the vision for student behavior and discipline. This involves creating clear policies that outline expectations and consequences, fostering a positive school climate. **Leadership and Support:** By modeling appropriate behavior and decision-making, the director sets a standard for both staff and students. They provide support and resources for teachers to implement discipline strategies effectively. **Communication:** The director communicates expectations and policies to students, parents, and staff. This transparency helps to build trust and ensures everyone is on the same page regarding behavior standards. **Professional Development:** They facilitate training for teachers on effective classroom management and restorative practices, equipping them with tools to handle behavioral issues proactively.

Role of the Vice-Director: The vice-director complements the director's efforts and often takes a more hands-on approach in day-to-day operations (Bingham, Nabatchi, & O'Leary, 2005). Their contributions include:

families establish home environments to support students.

1.6. Limitation

This study is limited to directors, vice-directors, committees, librarian, administrators, teachers, NGOs, and parents' students from 3 schools in Areiksat city concerning discipline practices in primary schools, focusing on grades 5 to 6. Analysis of data obtained is generalizable only to the participants in this study, rather than the generalizability readers might perceive from the qualitative findings (Nelson, 2002).

Implementation of Policies: The vice-director ensures that the policies set forth by the director are implemented effectively throughout the school. They work closely with teachers and staff to enforce rules consistently. **Conflict Resolution:** Acting as a mediator, the vice-director addresses conflicts between students and resolves disciplinary issues promptly, promoting a restorative rather than punitive approach. **Student Engagement:** The vice-director often leads initiatives that engage students in positive behavior, such as mentorship programs, peer mediation, and extracurricular activities that promote teamwork and respect. **Support for Teachers:** By providing immediate support and guidance to teachers facing behavioral challenges, the vice-director helps maintain a positive learning environment. They might also assist in developing individualized behavior plans for students. **Monitoring and Feedback:** The vice-director regularly observes classroom dynamics and provides feedback to teachers. This observational role is crucial for identifying best practices and areas for improvement (Nettles & Herrington, 2007). **Role of Parents/Guardians:** Parents play a critical role in shaping student behavior and supporting discipline efforts. Their involvement can include reinforcing behavioral expectations at home, engaging in open communication with school staff, attending parent-teacher conferences, and participating in disciplinary

interventions or programs (Patall, Cooper, & Robinson, 2008).

2.3. Indirect Stakeholders (Kyriakides et al., 2015).

Community Members: Local residents and businesses support student behavior improvement by offering resources, mentorship, and funding. **School Board Members:** Elected officials develop policies and allocate resources to enhance school discipline. **Education Researchers and Experts:** They conduct research and provide training to help educators manage student behavior effectively. **Government Agencies:** These bodies create policies and provide funding to promote positive student behavior and discipline in schools.

2.4. The challenges that stakeholders encountered in improving student behavior and school discipline.

Family Factors: A major challenge in student discipline is family dynamics, such as single-parent households. These families may lack the resources and time to effectively support their children's education, leading to poor communication with schools. Additionally, if parents show indifference toward education, it can negatively influence student attitudes and behavior (Sheldon, Epstein, & society, 2002). **Teacher Factors:** Teacher attitudes and workloads also pose significant challenges. Negative sentiment among teachers, often due to burnout or lack of support, can create an unproductive classroom environment. High workloads limit teachers' abilities to connect with students, which is essential for maintaining discipline (Chitiyo, Wheeler, & Education, 2009). **Peer Factors:** Peer relationships can adversely affect student behavior, as peers often exert pressure to conform to disruptive behaviors. This peer influence fosters a culture where misbehavior may be tolerated, complicating efforts to enforce discipline effectively (Luiselli, Putnam, Handler, & Feinberg, 2005). **Cultural Factors:** Cultural differences can lead to misunderstandings between students, teachers, and parents, which complicates the establishment of consistent disciplinary policies. Differences in communication styles and cultural norms may create friction in disciplinary settings (Sugai, O'Keeffe, & Fallon, 2012).

2.5. What has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behavior and school discipline.

School-Families Collaboration: Schools are enhancing collaboration with families by establishing regular communication through meetings, workshops, and newsletters to keep parents informed about

policies and their child's progress. Proactive engagement helps identify issues early and fosters shared responsibility for student behavior. Implementing restorative practices focuses on repairing harm from misbehavior, promoting accountability and empathy among students. Intervention programs that involve family participation provide support and resources to empower parents, creating a network that reinforces discipline and enhances student behavior (Meyer & Land, 2005). **Principal-Teacher Collaboration:** Schools are fostering collaboration between principals and teachers through professional development programs that equip educators with effective classroom management strategies. Regular meetings allow staff to discuss challenges, share best practices, and address specific discipline concerns. This builds a sense of community and morale among teachers. Open communication channels help teachers express their needs, while conflict resolution strategies address disagreements constructively, contributing to a supportive school climate that encourages positive student behavior (Cansoy & Parlar, 2018).

Classroom Management: Effective classroom management strategies are crucial for improving student behavior. Establishing clear rules and consistently enforcing them provides students with a framework for acceptable behavior. Building positive relationships between teachers and students fosters respect and engagement, motivating students to behave appropriately. Engaging instructional practices, such as collaborative activities and technology integration, are used to create a dynamic learning environment. These efforts aim to promote academic success while minimizing disruptions, establishing a positive school culture where students understand the importance of discipline and take responsibility for their actions (Siregar, Doloksaribu, & Prayuda, 2024).

By implementing these strategies, schools address challenges in student behavior and discipline, fostering collaborative partnerships and creating supportive learning environments that enhance overall student success.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study employs a qualitative approach, focusing on the context of Areiksat city in Kandal province. The sample comprises 30 participants selected from three primary schools. Participants include one director, one vice-director, one librarian, and seven teachers from each school, chosen through purposive sampling. The rationale for selecting the director is to gain insights

into the challenges and collaborative efforts with stakeholders to improve student behavior and school discipline. The vice-director is included due to their responsibilities in managing school discipline and administration. The librarian's participation is valuable as they can provide information based on students' reading habits, while the seven teachers, who possess higher education, commitment, and extensive experience, are expected to offer significant insights.

Data collection methods include interviews, group discussions, and classroom observations. Interviews will consist of open-ended questions directed towards the director and teachers to elicit their perspectives and experiences related to the research questions (Patton, 2009). Group discussions will involve the director, teachers, and 6-10 parents to facilitate dialogue about positive and negative behaviors as well as discipline-related themes (Rossouw, 2003).

For data analysis, a qualitative data analysis flowchart will be utilized, following a step-by-step guide (Ron Nelson et al., 2002). This process will involve reading the collected data and transcripts, labeling relevant pieces, and developing a matrix. Subsequent steps include identifying themes and subthemes, prioritizing the most important codes, categorizing the data, summarizing the findings through visual representations, and writing a detailed report of the results, explaining the connections among categories.

Ethical considerations are paramount throughout the research process. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants, ensuring the protection of their privacy and confidentiality, while minimizing any potential harm or discomfort. All information will be treated confidentially, and all stakeholders will participate voluntarily in answering the questions posed during the research.

4. RESEARCH FINDING

This research finding is to examine practice, perception, challenges, that stakeholders improve student behaviour and school discipline, what has been done to overcome, how the school principals collaborate with stakeholders and perceived by 30 respondents of two groups of direct stakeholders and indirect stakeholders in Areiksat city, Kandal province, Cambodia. This research analysis aims to explore the role of stakeholders in influencing student behavior and disciplining practices within educational settings. By examining the existing body of research and studies, we aim to highlight the significance of stakeholder involvement, both direct and indirect, in fostering positive student conduct.

As a result, analyzing the data associate with five themes. In this dissertation, I used the term of emergent themes instead of using coding data and subthemes in the place initial coding. The five themes are: 1) student behavior, 2) The challenges in improving student behavior, 3) What has been done to overcome the challenges, 4) School Discipline. Additionally, there were several subthemes identifies as well. The remaining portion of this chapter is structured around four group emergent themes, which correlate to each of the study's four objectives. The framework themes and sub themes are depicted in the following graphic.

4.1. Student Behavior

This section categorizes student behavior into themes and subthemes, highlighting positive and negative behaviors observed in schools.

- A. Positive Behaviors: These include participation in class, respect for teachers and peers, and taking care of the learning environment.
- B. Negative Behaviors: Issues such as bullying (verbal and physical) are discussed, indicating the challenges schools face in managing student conduct.

4.2. 4.2 School Discipline

This section outlines the disciplinary actions and regulations in place to manage student behavior.

- A. Disciplinary Actions: Various forms of punishment are included, such as academic penalties, verbal warnings, and labor as punishment.
- B. School Regulations: The chapter discusses guidelines like dress codes and punctuality, emphasizing the need for clear expectations to foster discipline.

4.3. Stakeholders Involved in Improving Student Behavior and School Discipline

This section identifies the roles of different stakeholders in promoting positive behavior and discipline.

Ministry Involvement: The Ministry develops policies and guidelines for schools.

School Involvement: Schools work on monitoring and support systems.

Teachers' Involvement: Teachers establish classroom rules and model appropriate behavior.

Parental Involvement: Parents are encouraged to reinforce positive behavior at home.

4.4. Challenges in Improving Student Behavior

The findings identify several challenges faced by stakeholders:

Family Factors: Issues such as poor collaboration with schools and negative family dynamics can hinder student behavior. **Teacher Factors:** Teacher burnout and lack of support can contribute to classroom management problems. **Peer Influence:** Disruptive peer behavior can impact individual students' conduct. **Cultural Factors:** Differences in communication styles and cultural misunderstandings can complicate discipline efforts.

4.5. Overcoming Challenges

This section describes strategies implemented to address the challenges identified:

School-Family Collaboration: Initiatives like home visits and social media communication help engage parents. **Principal-Teacher Collaboration:** Regular meetings and professional development support teachers in managing classrooms. **Classroom Management:** Establishing clear rules and routines fosters a positive learning environment.

Overall, Chapter 4 provides a comprehensive insight into the dynamics of student behavior and discipline within the context of Cambodian primary schools, highlighting both the challenges and the strategies for improvement.

5. DISCUSSION

The study showed the main points for research questions between literature and finding that consistent and inconsistent between on Stakeholder Involvement, the challenges, and school discipline.

5.1. Stakeholders Involvement in improving student behavior and school discipline.

Ministry: Developing Policies, Curriculum Integration, Monitoring and Evaluation Teacher Training. (Training and Coaching, Community and Family Involvement) (Sugai & Horner, 2006). **Schools:** monitoring and intervention, collaboration with staff, building relationships with parents. (Early Intervention, Collaboration with Families) (Skiba & Peterson, 2000). **Teachers:** establishing classroom rules, modelling behaviour, building relationships with students, collaborating with colleagues, communication with parents. (engage with parents, set regulation, Foster Student Responsibility) (Marzano & Marzano, 2003). **Parent:** modelling positive behaviour, collaboration with teachers. (build relationship with school) (Sheldon et al., 2002). **Monks:** teaching moral values, mindfulness and meditation practices.

5.2. The Stakeholders improving school discipline

Disciplinary action: academic punishment, verbal warning, school labor punishment. (school expulsion, principal referral, detention sentence, in-school

suspension, academic punishment) (Sugai & Horner, 2014). **School regulation:** dress code, punctuality, health and safety special education regulation. (embracing punctuality, keeping quiet, respecting each other, dressing code, cleaning classroom, dropping garbage) (Sugai & Horner, 2014).

5.3. The challenges that stakeholders encountered in improving student behavior and school discipline.

Family Factors: Poor collaboration with teachers, neighbors, no modeling behavior, no enough time, increase feeling attack. (Single-parent households, poor communication, Parental Attitudes) (Sheldon et al., 2002). **Teacher Factors:** Bad classroom behavior, lack of collaboration, classroom intervention not strong. (Teacher Attitudes, Workload) (Chitiyo et al., 2009). **Peer Factors:** Modeling of disruptive behavior, gang behavior, drug abuse, deceived attitude. (peer pressure, spoil behavior, drug abuse) (Luiselli et al., 2005). **Culture Factor:** inappropriate dancing art, Overt display of sexy clothes, disrespect behavior. (Communication Styles, Sexy clothes styles) (Sugai et al., 2012)

5.4. What has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behavior and school discipline.

School-families collaboration: home visit, social medial, regular update, parent workshops, counselling and guidance. (regularly engage parents, repairing harm, interventions misbehavior, (Meyer & Land, 2005) **Principal-teacher collaboration:** providing information, coaching and feedback. (professional development, regular meeting, open channels, conflict resolution) (Cansoy & Parlar, 2018). **School-pagoda collaboration:** creating Buddhist lesson, creating school ceremony, moral education, mindfulness and meditation practices. **Classroom management:** set clear rules, structure routine, behavioural intervention, positive relationship, slogan words. (Establishing Clear Rules, Building Teacher-Student, Engaging Instructional Practices) (Siregar et al., 2024).

6. Conclusion

6.1. Summary

Stakeholders Involvement: Active collaboration among stakeholders' direct stakeholders (school, parents/family, students), indirect stakeholders (ministry, volunteers, NGOs), limited collaboration from parents. **School Discipline:** Existing Schools discipline (academic punishment, verbal warning, school labor punishment, dress code and make up, punctuality, special education regulation). **The challenges:** The limited collaboration between teachers and families, peer influence, class size (too

many students), spreading culture (inappropriate dancing/art from foreigner, overt displays of sexy clothes, disrespectful behavior), improperly implementation of the school discipline. **To overcome the challenges:** The collaboration between direct and indirect stakeholders (home visit, social media, regular update, workshop and training parents how to solve the students problem), create counselling room to solve the problems such as: spread culture, sexy clothes, disrespect behavior, improperly school discipline, build relationship between school-pagoda (regular meeting, to listen to monks advise, celebrate ceremony to educate mind, students morality), foster students respect for school regulations (dress code and make up, punctuality, health and safety, special education regulations).

6.2. Suggestion for further study

Future research should focus on collecting the data from other stakeholders who were not included parents, monks, NGOs, village leaders, department and ministry education, to make the topic more comprehensive, and also students' activities were not observed. To make this research more extensive the next researchers should study countryside schools.

6.3. Recommendations

The strategies should improve student behavior and school discipline is collaboration among stakeholders:

Regular meeting (Directors should have meetings with teachers and parents to have workshops at the end of each semester to support student behavior).

School Regulation (Directors and teachers should motivate students to apply the regulation, display the regulation by praising and rewarding acknowledge self-regulated behaviors, encourage students to learn from each other's self-regulation techniques). **Foster to build relationship** (Teachers should build relationship with parents through home visits, social media communication apps, regular update, students, and staff about the school discipline policies)

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